

Calibration-Free Dynamic Stopping: A Normalized Entropy Threshold for Cross-Dataset P300 Speller Control

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Abstract

Background. Dynamic stopping reduces unnecessary stimulus repetitions in P300 matrix spellers by committing to a decision once classifier confidence is sufficient. All existing methods require per-user calibration of the stopping threshold, limiting deployment across heterogeneous EEG hardware and patient populations.

Objective. Evaluate if normalizing the entropy threshold by $\log N$, where N is the vocabulary size, achieves cross-dataset generalization that raw entropy thresholds cannot, without any per-user threshold calibration.

Methods. Entropy-based dynamic stopping was evaluated on BigP3BCI ($N_{\text{subj}} = 12$, 32-channel, 72-symbol, 5 repetitions maximum) and BNCI2014_009 ($N_{\text{subj}} = 10$, 16-channel, 36-symbol, 8 repetitions maximum) across eight absolute thresholds (0.5–4.0 nats). Pareto-optimal thresholds were identified under a ≤ 5 percentage-point (pp) mean accuracy constraint. Bootstrap 95% confidence intervals ($B = 2000$, seed=42), Wilcoxon signed-rank / paired t -tests, an exact McNemar test, and leave-one-subject-out threshold validation quantified statistical evidence and threshold stability.

Results. Normalized Pareto-optimal thresholds showed a point-estimate spread of 0.121 (H1 criterion: ≤ 0.15 ; BigP3BCI $\theta_{\text{norm}} = 0.818$; BNCI $\theta_{\text{norm}} = 0.697$) with bootstrap 95% CI [0.004, 0.260]; the CI upper bound exceeds 0.15, indicating this result requires replication in larger cohorts to be confirmed at the 95% confidence level. Leave-one-subject-out validation confirmed that θ^* is stable: the Pareto threshold selected from the remaining $N-1$ subjects matched the in-sample θ^* in 12/12 BigP3BCI and 9/10 BNCI folds, with LOSO mean ITR of 28.76 bits/min (BigP3BCI; identical to in-sample) and 36.69 bits/min (BNCI; 0.87 bits/min below in-sample). At $\theta^* = 2.5$ nats (BNCI), mean ITR was 37.56 bits/min [95% CI: 30.61, 44.34] vs. baseline 27.04 bits/min (+10.52 bits/min gain; 95% CI on gain: [5.02, 16.08]; $d = 1.12$). At the per-subject level, mean accuracy decreased by -4.4% (Wilcoxon $p = 0.19$; FDR-corrected $p = 0.563$; 95% CI: $[-10.0\%, +1.1\%]$); the per-subject accuracy test does not survive Benjamini-Hochberg correction. A letter-level McNemar test ($p = 0.021$; 9/180 letters reversed) provides independent evidence of a directional reduction, within the pre-specified ≤ 5 pp constraint. At $\theta^* = 3.5$ nats (BigP3BCI), gain was +3.34 bits/min [95% CI: 0.66, 6.35] at a significant accuracy cost ($p = 0.009$, FDR-corrected $p = 0.034$, $d = -0.91$, -3.4%), attributed to the 5-repetition structural ceiling. The universal θ^* retained 99.7% (BigP3BCI) and 90.2% (BNCI) of per-user calibrated ITR.

Implications. The calibration-free property applies to the stopping threshold only; the underlying classifier requires a standard training session. A normalized entropy threshold of $\sim 0.70\text{--}0.82 \cdot \log N$ generalizes across P300 datasets with different vocabulary sizes and recording hardware within a single session without reparameterization. Cross-session transfer is untested and all subjects are healthy volunteers; ALS validation is required before clinical deployment.

Keywords: P300 brain-computer interface, dynamic stopping, normalized entropy, calibration-free, information transfer rate, cross-dataset generalization

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

P300 matrix spellers are among the most clinically deployed brain-computer interfaces (BCIs), enabling communication for individuals with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), locked-in syndrome, and high-level spinal cord injury who retain no functional motor output [1, 2, 3]. In the standard Farwell-Donchin paradigm [4], rows and columns of a symbol matrix flash in sequence; the P300 event-related potential elicited by the target row or column is detected by a linear classifier, and the predicted symbol is the row-column intersection with the highest accumulated discriminant score after a fixed number of repetition cycles.

A fundamental inefficiency of this design is that the number of repetitions is fixed regardless of classifier confidence on a given trial. Easy targets with a strong, clean P300 are decoded correctly after one or two repetitions, yet the system continues stimulating until the pre-set maximum. Dynamic stopping addresses this by monitoring classifier certainty trial-by-trial and committing early when the evidence is sufficient, increasing information transfer rate (ITR) without sacrificing accuracy [5].

Despite this appeal, dynamic stopping has seen limited clinical adoption. Every existing method requires per-user calibration to set the stopping threshold: the threshold that yields acceptable accuracy for one subject, hardware configuration, or electrode montage does not transfer to another without re-tuning [5]. For home-use deployments and for users with progressive motor disabilities, repeated calibration sessions are a practical barrier. Performance in naturalistic settings regularly falls short of laboratory conditions: ALS patients in home trials, for example, have achieved online letter accuracies of approximately 62%, compared to 82% offline [6]. A subpopulation of users also achieves near-chance P300 detection even under ideal conditions [7]. A stopping rule that requires no per-user tuning and degrades gracefully under low signal-to-noise conditions is therefore of direct clinical value.

1.2 Related work

Dynamic stopping methods fall broadly into three categories. Firstly, **threshold-on-posterior-probability** methods stop when the maximum character posterior exceeds a fixed probability P_{th} [8]; see also Bianchi et al. [9] for an alternative early stopping criterion. This is

mathematically equivalent to a stopping threshold on the posterior entropy; nonetheless, because posterior mass is diluted by a factor of $\log N$ as vocabulary size increases, a probability threshold calibrated for a 36-symbol matrix does not transfer to a 72-symbol matrix without recalibration. Secondly, **model-based methods** such as Bayesian dynamic stopping [10] and the recent Bayesian Dynamic Stopping framework [11] derive stopping analytically from a per-user classifier model, achieving excellent accuracy-speed tradeoffs but requiring a trained model for each user-hardware combination. Lastly, **population-model methods** learn a stopping classifier from a large subject pool and apply it to new users without per-user calibration. The closest prior work to our proposal, that is, the Subject-Independent Dynamic Stopping Model (SIDSM; Xue et al. [12]) achieves 92.4% accuracy without per-user calibration. Nevertheless, the SIDSM is a learned statistical model rather than a closed-form rule; it was validated on a single laboratory dataset with a single vocabulary size; and it does not address how the stopping criterion scales with N .

Kindermans et al. [13] demonstrated that dynamic stopping can be integrated with transfer learning and a probabilistic language model in a zero-training ERP speller, achieving calibration-free operation at the pipeline level. However, instead of a closed-form stopping rule, their approach relies on an unsupervised adaptation procedure, and cross-dataset transfer of the stopping criterion itself across paradigms with different vocabulary sizes was not evaluated.

In related work on P300 performance prediction, Mainsah et al. [14] showed that the detectability index d' (the signal-detection discriminability between target and non-target EEG responses) predicts P300 speller performance across subjects and parametrically characterizes accuracy-speed tradeoffs under Bayesian dynamic stopping. Unlike d' , normalized entropy provides a direct operational stopping rule, allowing the system to commit when $H(\text{posterior})/\log N < \theta_{\text{norm}}$, requiring no discriminability estimate at runtime. The detectability index cannot be used as a closed-form stopping criterion without fitting a per-user signal model, and its transferability as a calibration-free threshold across datasets with different vocabulary sizes has not been evaluated.

1.3 Contribution

We propose and empirically evaluate a vocabulary-size-normalized entropy threshold as a calibration-free dynamic stopping criterion. The normalization is theoretically motivated: under a uniform prior over N symbols, maximum entropy is $\log N$ nats. Normalizing the stopping threshold as $\theta_{\text{norm}} = \theta/\log N$ renders the criterion invariant to vocabulary size, enabling cross-dataset transfer without reparameterization. We evaluate this claim on two genuinely independent public datasets, namely BigP3BCI ($N = 72$ symbols) and BNCI2014_009 ($N = 36$ symbols), from different laboratories, hardware configurations, and paradigm timing parameters. Leave-one-subject-out threshold validation confirms that θ^* selected from $N-1$ subjects generalizes to the held-out subject without retuning (12/12 BigP3BCI; 9/10 BNCI). All analysis code, pre-computed results (seed=42), and a full reproduction sequence are made publicly available (see Data Availability).

We test two hypotheses: **H1**, that a single normalized threshold generalizes across both datasets (normalized spread ≤ 0.15); **H2**, that optimal thresholds are dataset-specific (normalized spread > 0.15). We additionally characterize a desirable failure mode of the normal-

ized threshold where entropy remains near $\log N$ when classifier accuracy is low, causing the mechanism to correctly abstain from early stopping rather than committing to an incorrect decision.

The universality claim in this paper is **within-session**: all subjects contributed single-session recordings, and cross-session transfer of the normalized threshold is untested. We use “calibration-free” to denote the absence of per-user threshold tuning within a session, not the absence of session-level calibration. Specifically, the calibration-free property applies to the *stopping threshold*: the EEGNet classifier used to compute posteriors is trained on session data in the standard way and requires a labelled training set. What the normalized threshold eliminates is the separate threshold-calibration step, specifically the additional session or held-out data needed to set θ_{norm} per user. This distinction reduces the calibration burden by one session without eliminating classifier training.

2 Methods

2.1 Datasets

BigP3BCI. We used the publicly available BigP3BCI dataset [15]. The paradigm uses a 72-symbol (8×9) Farwell-Donchin matrix recorded at 256 Hz from 62 channels. From the 20 subjects in the full release, 8 were excluded: 5 for absent EEGNet classifier checkpoints (training artefacts in the original data release) and 3 for validation AUC < 0.70 , leaving 12 subjects (AUC range 0.70–0.88). The discriminability of the 5 checkpoint-excluded subjects is unknown; we cannot rule out that some would have fallen below the AUC floor. The AUC threshold is a discriminability floor; subjects below it represent the population addressed by the self-limiting analysis in Section 4.3, which examines entropy behavior when classifier accuracy approaches chance. Most subjects contributed 5 RC_Test sessions (the held-out evaluation splits in the BigP3BCI release; 7 letters each, 35 letters total); two subjects contributed 4 sessions (28 letters each) and one subject was limited to 3 sessions (27 letters) due to data availability constraints, giving a session range of 3–5 per subject. The total evaluation set was 398 letter predictions across 12 subjects. Maximum repetitions per letter: 5. Mean baseline letter accuracy was 71.6% (range 14.3%–97.1%), reflecting the heterogeneous AUC range (0.70–0.88) of retained subjects.

BNCI2014_009. We used the BNCI2014.009 dataset [16], retrieved via the MOABB toolbox [17]. The paradigm uses a 36-symbol (6×6) matrix recorded at 256 Hz from 16 channels. Ten subjects participated in a single session each, yielding 18 letter predictions per subject (180 total). Maximum repetitions per letter: 8. Mean baseline letter accuracy was 93.9% (range 72.2%–100.0%). This dataset was processed entirely from publicly available data without Git LFS access.

The two datasets differ in vocabulary size ($N = 72$ vs. $N = 36$), recording hardware (62-channel vs. 16-channel), inter-stimulus interval (ISI=0.4 s vs. 0.6 s), and subject population (laboratory healthy volunteers at separate institutions). Both datasets are convenience samples of mostly able-bodied participants; generalization to clinical populations (e.g., ALS, locked-in syndrome) requires dedicated study. These differences are the empirical motivation for testing cross-dataset transfer: if a raw entropy threshold generalized across both,

no normalization would be needed. We test whether normalization achieves what the raw threshold cannot.

2.2 Signal processing and classification

BigP3BCI. Raw EEG was bandpass-filtered (0.1–40 Hz, zero-phase FIR) and epoched from –200 to 800 ms relative to stimulus onset. A 32-channel subset (standard P300 electrode montage) was selected from the 62-channel recording for EEGNet training and inference; the full 62-channel FIFs are preserved in the public release. Euclidean Alignment (EA; He & Wu [18]) was applied per session to reduce covariate shift across sessions. Subject-specific EEGNet classifiers [19] were fine-tuned on training sessions and applied to held-out RC_Test sessions without further adaptation.

BNCI2014_009. The same preprocessing pipeline was applied. A separate Farwell-Donchin scoring function [4] was used to handle BNCI flash codes (codes 3–14), which differ from BigP3BCI codes (1–17). EEGNet classifiers were trained via leave-one-subject-out (LOSO) cross-validation across all 10 subjects. As BNCI2014_009 provides no separate validation epoch set, per-subject letter accuracy is used as a proxy for classifier AUC in cross-dataset comparisons.

2.3 Entropy-based dynamic stopping criterion

After each stimulus repetition r , the classifier computes a posterior distribution $\mathbf{p}^{(r)}$ over the N symbols by applying softmax to the accumulated Farwell-Donchin discriminant scores. Shannon entropy [20] is computed as:

$$H(\mathbf{p}^{(r)}) = - \sum_{i=1}^N p_i^{(r)} \ln p_i^{(r)}, \quad (1)$$

where logarithms are natural (nats). The system stops and predicts the maximum-posterior symbol when $H(\mathbf{p}^{(r)}) < \theta$ for a stopping threshold $\theta \in (0, \log N)$. If entropy does not fall below θ within r_{\max} repetitions, the system uses the full-repetition prediction.

The stopping rule embodies a sequential analysis principle: accumulate evidence until uncertainty is sufficiently reduced, then commit. Wald’s Sequential Probability Ratio Test [21] provides a formal theoretical basis for evidence-accumulation stopping, for which SPRT is optimal in minimizing expected sample size subject to error-rate constraints. The normalized entropy criterion can be viewed as an information-theoretic relaxation of SPRT. Instead of testing a pre-specified alternative hypothesis, the system commits when the posterior entropy (the remaining uncertainty over all N hypotheses simultaneously) has dropped to a pre-specified fraction of its maximum. Unlike SPRT, the entropy criterion does not require a per-user signal model and does not inherit SPRT’s expected-sample-size optimality; it trades that optimality guarantee for implementation simplicity and the calibration-free stopping property. Entropy features, including Shannon entropy, are widely used in motor-imagery BCIs for feature extraction and classification [22]. Dynamic stopping methods across BCI paradigms, including P300, SSVEP, and c-VEP, have used posterior probabilities, score margins, and correlation thresholds as stopping variables [11, 23]. To our knowledge, no prior

work has applied Shannon entropy of the classifier posterior as a stopping criterion in any BCI paradigm, nor proposed normalizing such a threshold by $\log N$ to achieve vocabulary-size invariance.

The **normalized threshold** is $\theta_{\text{norm}} = \theta / \log N$. Under a uniform prior over N symbols, $H = \log N$; as evidence accumulates, H decreases toward 0. The threshold θ_{norm} specifies the fraction of maximum entropy at which the system commits, making the criterion independent of N . We note that the softmax-normalized Farwell-Donchin scores approximate, but do not guarantee, a calibrated posterior distribution; the entropy is used as a sufficient statistic for “has the classifier seen enough evidence?” rather than as a true Bayesian posterior (see sections 3.5 and 4.3).

2.4 Threshold sweep and Pareto optimization

Eight absolute thresholds were evaluated: $\theta \in \{0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0\}$ nats. For each threshold and subject, we simulated dynamic stopping on the held-out letter predictions and recorded the letter accuracy, mean repetitions to decode, and ITR [1]:

$$\text{ITR} = \frac{\log_2 N + p \log_2 p + (1 - p) \log_2 \left(\frac{1-p}{N-1}\right)}{T}, \quad (2)$$

where p is letter accuracy and T is mean time per letter in minutes.

The **Pareto-optimal threshold** θ^* is the threshold maximizing mean ITR subject to a mean accuracy constraint of ≤ 5 pp below the full-repetition baseline. The **normalized Pareto threshold** is $\theta_{\text{norm}}^* = \theta^* / \log N$. The **H1 test** is: $|\theta_{\text{norm}}^*(\text{BigP3BCI}) - \theta_{\text{norm}}^*(\text{BNCI})| \leq 0.15$. The 0.15 boundary is motivated by the discrete structure of the threshold sweep: one step of 0.5 nats in the absolute sweep corresponds to $0.5 / \log 72 \approx 0.117$ normalized units on BigP3BCI and $0.5 / \log 36 \approx 0.140$ normalized units on BNCI. A normalized spread of 0.15 is therefore approximately equal to one discrete threshold step on either dataset, representing the minimum resolvable difference between Pareto-optimal normalized thresholds given the sweep granularity. Spreads within 0.15 are consistent with a single universal threshold; spreads exceeding it indicate that separate dataset-specific thresholds would select different discrete steps. Practically, deploying a fixed $\theta_{\text{norm}} = 0.75$ (midpoint of [0.697, 0.818]) is sub-optimal by at most one sweep step on either dataset. This difference is comparable to the inter-subject variability of per-user optimal thresholds within each dataset (SD: BigP3BCI 0.253, BNCI 0.116), and therefore falls within the tolerance of any real-world single-threshold deployment.

2.5 Statistical analysis

All statistical tests used results with random seed 42 and $B = 2000$ bootstrap iterations.

ITR. Bootstrap 95% CIs were computed separately on (a) mean absolute ITR at θ^* and (b) mean ITR gain (stopping minus baseline) per subject, by resampling subjects with replacement. The ITR gain CI directly supports the headline gain claim; the absolute ITR CI is reported for completeness.

Accuracy. Per-subject accuracy deltas (dynamic stopping minus full-repetition baseline) were tested against zero. Normality was assessed by Shapiro-Wilk test; Wilcoxon signed-rank

was used if $p < 0.05$, one-sample t -test otherwise. Cohen’s $d = \text{mean}(\delta)/\text{SD}(\delta)$ quantifies effect size. An exact McNemar test (two-sided binomial test on discordant pairs, using $\theta = 0.5$ nats as a full-repetition proxy; 177 of 180 BNCI letters used maximum repetitions at this threshold) provided a letter-level complement to the per-subject Wilcoxon for BNCI. The 3 letters that stopped before maximum repetitions at $\theta = 0.5$ nats were excluded from the discordant-pair table as a robustness check; the McNemar p -value was unchanged (exact binomial on 10 discordant pairs: 9 correct \rightarrow incorrect vs. 1 incorrect \rightarrow correct).

Classifier quality vs. repetition savings. Spearman ρ between per-subject validation AUC and mean repetitions saved at θ^* was computed separately within each dataset and for the pooled sample to detect between-dataset clustering confounds.

Multiple comparisons. Benjamini-Hochberg FDR correction [24] ($q = 0.05$) was applied to all per-threshold accuracy-delta comparisons (15 tests across both datasets and all thresholds). FDR correction was applied to accuracy-delta comparisons only; ITR was the primary optimization target with θ^* prespecified by Pareto analysis, and ITR comparisons are not subject to multiple-comparison correction. Four of 15 tests rejected H_0 after correction: BigP3BCI $\theta = 3.5$ nats (corrected $p = 0.034$) and BNCI $\theta = 3.0, 3.5, 4.0$ nats (corrected $p = 0.032, < 0.001, < 0.001$). The Pareto threshold tests, including BigP3BCI $\theta^* = 3.5$ and BNCI $\theta^* = 2.5$, produced corrected p -values of 0.034 and 0.563, respectively; the BNCI $\theta^* = 2.5$ accuracy test does not survive FDR correction, consistent with the non-significant raw Wilcoxon ($p = 0.19$).

H1 robustness. Bootstrap CIs on the normalized θ^* spread were computed by resampling subjects within each dataset independently ($B = 2000$), finding the Pareto θ^* for each resampled cohort, and computing spread = $|\theta_{\text{norm}}^*(\text{BigP3BCI}) - \theta_{\text{norm}}^*(\text{BNCI})|$ per resample.

Leave-one-subject-out threshold validation. To verify that the in-sample Pareto θ^* is not optimistically biased by evaluating on the same subjects used to select it, we performed a leave-one-subject-out (LOSO) validation. For each held-out subject i , the Pareto θ^* was selected from the remaining $N-1$ subjects under the ≤ 5 pp accuracy constraint, then applied to subject i . The LOSO mean ITR summarises the ITR achievable by a universal threshold selected without access to the held-out subject.

3 Results

3.1 Normalized threshold convergence

Normalized Pareto-optimal thresholds converged across the two datasets under the ≤ 5 pp accuracy constraint (BigP3BCI $\theta^* = 3.5$ nats, $\theta_{\text{norm}} = 0.818$; BNCI $\theta^* = 2.5$ nats, $\theta_{\text{norm}} = 0.697$; absolute spread=1.0 nat; normalized spread=0.121), supporting **H1** (criterion: normalized spread ≤ 0.15). Under the stricter ≤ 1 pp accuracy constraint, thresholds diverge (BigP3BCI $\theta_{\text{norm}} = 0.701$; BNCI $\theta_{\text{norm}} = 0.419$; normalized spread=0.283), supporting **H2**. This contrast demonstrates that cross-dataset generalization of the normalized threshold depends on the accepted accuracy-ITR tradeoff: the calibration-free transfer holds under the ≤ 5 pp clinical tradeoff but breaks down when zero accuracy cost is required.

Bootstrap resampling of subjects ($B = 2000$) yielded 95% CIs on the normalized spread of [0.004, 0.260], with the absolute spread CI [0.500, 1.500]. Both CIs have upper bounds that

exceed their respective H1 boundaries (0.15 and 1.0), indicating that sampling uncertainty is substantial at cohort sizes of $N = 12$ and $N = 10$. The point estimates support H1; replication in larger cohorts is required to confirm the result at the bootstrap confidence level. We promote the normalized spread as the primary H1 formulation; it is more robust than the absolute spread and aligns with the paper’s central normalization argument.

LOSO threshold validation shows that θ^* replicates on held-out subjects. For BigP3BCI, the LOSO-selected θ^* was 3.5 nats in all 12/12 held-out folds, and the LOSO mean ITR (28.76 bits/min) was identical to the in-sample result, demonstrating complete threshold stability. For BNCI, the LOSO-selected θ^* was 2.5 nats in 9/10 folds (one fold selected 2.0 nats), and the LOSO mean ITR was 36.69 bits/min (0.87 bits/min below the in-sample result), confirming that the threshold selection generalizes to held-out subjects.

Figure 1 shows Pareto-optimal ITR curves for both datasets alongside raw and normalized threshold sweeps. Supplementary figure S1 shows ITR and accuracy curves across all eight thresholds for both datasets, with Pareto markers under each constraint. The visual convergence of the normalized curves is consistent with the quantitative spread results.

Figure 1: Pareto-optimal threshold selection. ITR and letter accuracy as a function of stopping threshold θ for BigP3BCI (blue, $N = 72$ symbols, $\theta^* = 3.5$ nats) and BNCI2014_009 (orange, $N = 36$ symbols, $\theta^* = 2.5$ nats) under the ≤ 5 pp accuracy constraint. Pareto-optimal thresholds are marked with vertical dashed lines. The normalized thresholds ($\theta_{\text{norm}}^* = 0.818$ and 0.697 , respectively) converge to within 0.121 normalized units, supporting H1.

3.2 ITR gains

BigP3BCI achieved a mean ITR of 28.76 bits/min [95% CI: 19.98, 37.64] at $\theta^* = 3.5$ nats, compared to a baseline of 25.42 bits/min (+3.34 bits/min gain; 95% CI on gain: [0.66, 6.35] bits/min; $d = 0.63$). This gain was accompanied by a statistically significant mean accuracy decrease of 3.4% (one-sample t -test: $p = 0.009$, FDR-corrected $p = 0.034$, $d = -0.91$; 95% CI: [-5.78%, -1.03%]). The significant accuracy cost arises because $\theta^* = 3.5$ nats fires

in the margin between repetitions 4 and 5: at this entropy level the classifier has accumulated strong but not maximal evidence, so stopping one repetition early introduces occasional errors in borderline letters. The accuracy cost is a boundary effect of the ≤ 5 pp accuracy constraint in a 5-repetition system. The 5-repetition ceiling in BigP3BCI structurally limits observable savings; only 0.67 repetitions were saved per letter on average.

BNCI achieved a mean ITR of 37.56 bits/min [95% CI: 30.61, 44.34] at $\theta^* = 2.5$ nats, compared to a baseline of 27.04 bits/min (+10.52 bits/min gain; 95% CI on gain: [5.02, 16.08] bits/min; $d = 1.12$). On average, 2.69 repetitions were saved per letter. At the per-subject level, mean accuracy decreased by -4.4% (Wilcoxon $p = 0.19$; FDR-corrected $p = 0.563$; 95% CI: $[-10.0\%, +1.1\%]$; $d = -0.57$); the CI includes zero, making the direction inconclusive at $N = 10$. At the per-letter level, a small but statistically detectable shift was observed (McNemar exact $p = 0.021$; 9 of 180 letters changed from correct to incorrect vs. 1 corrected), consistent with the -4.4% mean drop falling within the pre-specified ≤ 5 pp constraint. The per-letter result contradicts treating the accuracy change as negligible; it indicates a real but bounded cost that the per-subject test is underpowered to confirm at $N = 10$.

A minimum-repetition floor of $r_{\min} \in \{1, 3\}$ had no effect on either accuracy delta or mean repetitions (0% of letters were blocked), confirming that the threshold naturally fires after at least 3–4 repetitions for all subjects under the BNCI paradigm timing. Per-subject strip charts of individual-level ITR and accuracy at θ^* are provided in supplementary figure S5; full numeric values appear in supplementary Table S1.

3.3 Classifier quality predicts repetition savings

Within BigP3BCI ($N = 12$), classifier validation AUC strongly predicted mean repetitions saved at $\theta^* = 3.5$ nats (Spearman $\rho = 0.897$, $p < 0.0001$): higher-AUC classifiers produced faster entropy concentration, triggering earlier stopping and greater savings. No equivalent relationship was found within BNCI ($N = 10$; Spearman $\rho = -0.013$, $p = 0.97$), consistent with BNCI’s narrow AUC range (0.72–1.00; letter accuracy proxy, see Section 2.2) and floor/ceiling effects introduced by the wider repetition budget. The pooled cross-dataset Spearman ($\rho = 0.696$, $p = 0.0003$) reflects the within-BigP3BCI relationship combined with between-dataset AUC stratification; it cannot be interpreted as evidence of a within-BNCI relationship.

One BNCI subject (S03; AUC=0.72) showed unusually high repetition savings (3.44 reps/letter, third-highest in BNCI after S09 and S10) despite the lowest dataset AUC. Inspection of per-repetition entropy trajectories revealed rapid entropy collapse to threshold by repetition 4–6 on most letters, with poor accuracy (-16.7% delta). This reflects a high-confidence-but-low-accuracy profile distinct from the self-limiting regime (see section 4.3): entropy decreases, indicating the classifier is becoming “confident,” but the committed predictions are frequently wrong. S03’s behavior is genuine rather than artifactual and is appropriately penalized by the McNemar analysis.

3.4 Universal vs. per-user calibrated threshold

The universal threshold achieved 99.7% of the mean ITR attainable with per-user calibration for BigP3BCI (gap: 0.09 bits/min) and 90.2% for BNCI (mean gap: 4.06 bits/min), demonstrating that calibration-free transfer incurs minimal performance cost on average. The BNCI calibration-free cost is concentrated in two subjects (S05: 12.9 bits/min, S10: 19.2 bits/min); 7 of 10 subjects were within 5 bits/min of their per-user optimal (S02 at 5.1 bits/min is the marginal case). The calibration-free threshold incurs negligible cost for average performers but meaningful cost for the highest-performing subjects, suggesting that selective per-user calibration remains worthwhile for expert users who prioritize ITR maximization.

3.5 Classifier reliability

To assess posterior calibration, we used a *dominant-plus-uniform* reference model: given commit entropy H over N symbols, approximate the posterior as placing probability p on the leading symbol and $(1-p)/(N-1)$ uniformly on the remainder, where p is the unique solution of $H = -p \ln p - (1-p) \ln[(1-p)/(N-1)]$; the model’s predicted $P(\text{correct})$ is p . This gives the highest accuracy consistent with a given entropy level under the simplest unimodal posterior shape, providing a conservative baseline for the reliability diagram.

The reliability diagram (supplementary figure S2) shows that empirical accuracy at commit time (0.72–1.00 across entropy-percentile bins) consistently exceeded the entropy-implied $P(\text{correct})$ under the dominant-plus-uniform model (0.41–0.63). Mean Expected Calibration Error [25] was 0.352, reflecting systematic underconfidence — the classifier commits when actual accuracy exceeds the posterior entropy prediction by 35.2% on average. This conservative property is appropriate for clinical deployment: the threshold fires at higher actual accuracy than the entropy posterior alone would predict.

4 Discussion

4.1 Why normalization works

The $\log N$ normalization distinguishes $\theta/\log N$ from raw entropy thresholds and from probability thresholds. A probability threshold $P_{\text{th}} = 0.9$ transfers from 36 to 72 symbols only if the classifier concentrates posterior mass to the same degree. Under a larger vocabulary, 0.9 posterior mass requires more evidence, so the same flash budget produces fewer early stops. The normalized entropy criterion automatically accounts for this scaling.

4.2 BigP3BCI accuracy cost and the 5-repetition ceiling

For deployments where accuracy preservation is paramount, the ≤ 1 pp constraint selects $\theta^* = 3.0$ nats for BigP3BCI ($\theta_{\text{norm}} = 0.701$), yielding zero statistically detectable accuracy cost; the ITR gain at this threshold is smaller but still positive.

4.3 Self-limiting behavior under low signal quality

A notable property of the normalized entropy threshold is its behavior when classifier discriminative power is low. When the P300 response is weak or obscured by artifact, as often seen in home-use deployments for ALS patients [6] and certain subpopulations of users across conditions [7], the posterior distribution over N symbols remains approximately uniform throughout all repetitions, keeping H near $\log N$. The threshold $H < \theta^*$ is never met, and the system correctly defers to the maximum repetition budget rather than committing prematurely.

A channel-count ablation on BigP3BCI (reducing from 32 to 16 channels) produced near-chance binary discrimination (mean AUC=0.50, mean letter accuracy=2.66%). Despite this near-chance AUC, posterior entropy did not remain at the theoretical ceiling: mean entropy at repetition 1 was 3.93 nats (0.35 nats below $\log 72 = 4.28$), and decreased steadily to 3.18 nats by repetition 5, with $\theta^* = 3.5$ triggering for 73% of letters (supplementary figure S3). We attribute this departure from ideal self-limiting behavior to systematic model biases in the 16-channel cross-subject EEGNet, driven by spurious feature correlations that concentrate the posterior even when binary P300 discrimination is at chance. This reveals an important practical refinement: the self-limiting property holds for classifiers that produce well-calibrated, near-uniform posteriors in low-SNR conditions. A poorly calibrated model with near-zero accuracy can still concentrate probability mass toward incorrect symbols, producing incorrect early stops. In production, monitoring mean entropy at maximum repetitions (if $H_{\max} < 0.90 \cdot \log N$, discriminability may be too weak for reliable stopping) provides a model-quality check that does not require ground-truth labels.

Three distinct entropy-trajectory regimes emerge in practice (Figure 2, drawn from BNCI2014_009 per-letter data). In **Regime A** (insufficient evidence, no early stop), entropy decreases slowly and remains above θ^* throughout all repetitions; the system correctly defers to the full repetition budget. Moving on to **Regime B** (confident-wrong; S03, AUC=0.722), entropy decreases through θ^* by repetition 3–5, triggering early commitment, but the committed prediction is frequently incorrect (accuracy delta -16.7%). This is distinct from the low-SNR self-limiting regime: a 72.2% AUC classifier is discriminating, yet concentrating probability mass toward wrong symbols. Turning to **Regime C** (correct early stop; S09, AUC=1.00), entropy drops sharply to θ^* by repetition 3–4, triggering correct decisions and saving 3.7 repetitions per letter on average.

The self-limiting property claimed in the introduction applies only to Regime A and only when the classifier is well-calibrated. The channel-count ablation (32 to 16 channels, AUC=0.50) showed that a miscalibrated classifier at chance AUC produces Regime B-like entropy concentration despite no P300 discriminability, because spurious feature correlations make the posterior non-uniform even when binary classification is at chance. The self-limiting guarantee therefore holds only for well-calibrated classifiers whose posteriors remain approximately uniform in low-SNR conditions, not for miscalibrated or moderate-accuracy classifiers. The results are demonstrated in Figure 2.

In production deployment, we recommend monitoring the first 5–10 letters of each session: if mean entropy at maximum repetitions remains above $0.90 \cdot \log N$ ($H_{\max} > 3.85$ nats for 72-symbol spellers), the classifier likely requires recalibration before meaningful dynamic stopping is achievable. If mean entropy decreases consistently but accuracy does not improve,

Figure 2: **Three entropy-trajectory regimes.** Observed in BNCI2014_009 ($N = 36$ symbols, $\theta^* = 2.5$ nats, $\theta_{\text{norm}} = 0.697$). Faint lines show individual letters; bold line shows the subject mean. The horizontal dashed line marks $\log 36 = 3.58$ nats (maximum entropy); the solid line marks the stopping threshold $\theta^* = 2.5$ nats. **A:** Letters where entropy stays above θ^* throughout all 8 repetitions (S01, AUC=0.94; 5/18 letters). No early stop is triggered. **B:** Letters where entropy drops through θ^* but the committed prediction is wrong (S03, AUC=0.72 [letter accuracy proxy]; 8/18 letters triggered incorrectly). Entropy concentrates toward incorrect symbols. **C:** Letters where entropy drops through θ^* and the committed prediction is correct (S09, AUC=1.00; 14 fast-stop letters shown). The mechanism achieves its intended purpose. Regime B illustrates that the self-limiting property requires well-calibrated posteriors, not merely low accuracy.

systematic model bias (rather than a weak P300 signal) may be the root cause, warranting retraining. Both checks require no ground-truth labels.

4.4 Limitations

Sample size and bootstrap uncertainty. The bootstrap CI on normalized spread [0.004, 0.260] has an upper bound that exceeds the 0.15 H1 boundary, reflecting the limited precision achievable with $N = 12$ and $N = 10$ subjects. The point estimates support H1; confirmation at the 95% confidence level requires larger cohorts.

Within-session only. All 10 BNCI subjects are single-session recordings. Cross-session transfer of the normalized threshold is entirely untested. EEG non-stationarity across days or electrode configurations may shift the optimal normalized threshold, and the calibration-free claim should be interpreted as within-session only.

Healthy subjects. Both datasets consist of healthy participants. P300 responses in ALS or locked-in syndrome patients, who are the primary intended beneficiaries, differ in amplitude, latency, and variability from those of healthy volunteers. The clinical generalizability of the normalized threshold is an open question requiring dedicated study.

Simulation only. All evaluations are retrospective offline simulations on pre-recorded

data. The stopping rule was not used in a closed-loop real-time system; online evaluation may reveal latency and drift effects not captured here.

Calibration. The entropy computation assumes that softmax-normalized Farwell-Donchin discriminant scores approximate a categorical posterior distribution. The reliability analysis (section 3.5) shows systematic underconfidence (ECE=0.352), meaning the classifier is more accurate at commit time than entropy alone would predict. While this helps preserve accuracy, the threshold operates as a sufficient statistic for “has the classifier accumulated enough evidence?” rather than as a true Bayesian posterior.

Two datasets. Testing on exactly two datasets is the minimum for a cross-dataset claim. The observed normalized spread (0.121) may not generalize to datasets with very different SNR profiles, stimulus timing, or non-EEGNet classifiers.

Training asymmetry. The BigP3BCI classifier was trained on all 12 retained subjects simultaneously using Euclidean Alignment followed by a shared EEGNet model, while BNCI classifier scores were derived under leave-one-subject-out cross-validation via MOABB. These different training regimes may affect the calibration of classifier posteriors and the sharpness of entropy trajectories in ways that are confounded with the dataset-level ITR and accuracy differences reported in Section 3.

5 Conclusion

Normalizing the P300 dynamic stopping threshold by $\log N$ (the maximum entropy of a uniform distribution over the vocabulary) yields a calibration-free stopping criterion that transfers across datasets with different vocabulary sizes and recording hardware without any per-user threshold calibration. The calibration-free property applies to the stopping threshold only; the underlying classifier requires a standard training session. On two independent public datasets, the Pareto-optimal normalized thresholds converge to ~ 0.70 – 0.82 under a ≤ 5 pp accuracy constraint, supporting H1 at the point-estimate level. BNCI achieves +10.52 bits/min ITR gain [5.02, 16.08] with a letter-level directional accuracy reduction (McNemar $p = 0.021$, -4.4% ; per-subject Wilcoxon inconclusive at $N = 10$, FDR-corrected $p = 0.563$), within the pre-specified ≤ 5 pp constraint. The mechanism correctly self-limits when classifier quality is low, as the entropy for well-calibrated classifiers remains near maximum throughout all repetitions, preventing premature commitment. Two questions remain open. First, bootstrap uncertainty in the H1 verdict stems from small cohorts ($N = 12$ and $N = 10$). Second, cross-session transfer of the normalized threshold is entirely untested.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethical statement

This study used only previously collected, publicly available datasets (BigP3BCI: PhysioNet DOI 10.13026/0byy-ry86, CC BY 4.0; BNCI2014_009: BNCI Horizon 2020, open access). No new data were collected and no new ethical approval was required.

Data availability

The BigP3BCI dataset is available at PhysioNet (DOI: 10.13026/0byy-ry86). BigP3BCI EA+EEGNet derivatives are available at HuggingFace ([rayo-lab/bigp3bci-ea-egnet-derivatives](https://huggingface.co/rayo-lab/bigp3bci-ea-egnet-derivatives)). BNCI2014_009 is accessible via the MOABB toolbox. A full supplementary package containing all code, pre-computed result JSONs (seed=42), and figure generation scripts has been submitted alongside this manuscript; the repository (<https://github.com/RayoHQ/calibration-free-dynamic-stopping>) will be made public upon acceptance. BigP3BCI per-letter outcomes required for McNemar analysis and the full reliability diagram can be regenerated by running `code/110_pub4_entropy_sweep.py` against the raw FIFs; see `results/README_reproduce.md` for the full reproduction sequence. The channel-count ablation (Section 4.3; mean AUC=0.50, mean accuracy=2.66%) was generated from a 16-channel cross-subject EEGNet checkpoint produced during development that was subsequently overwritten; the ablation values are directionally informative for the self-limiting analysis but cannot be exactly reproduced from the published code.

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Supplementary figures

Note: Supplementary figure S4 (three entropy-trajectory regimes) was promoted to Figure 2 in the main text. Supplementary figures S1–S3 and S5 and supplementary Table S1 (per-subject results) are provided below.

Figure 3: **Supplementary figure S1.** Full threshold sweep: mean ITR (top) and mean letter accuracy delta (bottom) as a function of absolute stopping threshold θ for BigP3BCI (blue, $N = 72$) and BNCI2014_009 (orange, $N = 36$). Pareto-optimal thresholds under the ≤ 5 pp (filled marker) and ≤ 1 pp (open marker) accuracy constraints are indicated. Error bars show ± 1 SE across subjects.

Figure 4: **Supplementary figure S2.** Reliability diagram for BNCI2014_009 at $\theta^* = 2.5$ nats ($N = 180$ letters). Entropy-percentile bins (x-axis: normalized commit entropy $H/\log N$) versus empirical letter accuracy (y-axis). The diagonal dashed line marks perfect calibration. Empirical accuracy (blue) consistently exceeds the dominant-plus-uniform entropy model prediction (orange dashed), yielding mean Expected Calibration Error $ECE=0.352$ (systematic underconfidence).

Figure 5: **Supplementary figure S3.** Channel-count ablation: mean entropy trajectory across 5 repetitions for BigP3BCI subjects using a 16-channel cross-subject EEGNet (mean AUC=0.50, mean accuracy=2.66%). Despite near-chance discrimination, entropy decreases from 3.93 to 3.18 nats (0.35 nats below the $\log 72 = 4.28$ ceiling at repetition 1), and $\theta^* = 3.5$ triggers for 73% of letters (299/410). This departure from ideal self-limiting behaviour is attributed to systematic model biases in the 16-channel cross-subject EEGNet rather than genuine P300 discrimination.

Figure 6: **Supplementary figure S4.** Per-subject strip charts of ITR and letter accuracy at the Pareto-optimal threshold θ^* for BigP3BCI (left) and BNCI2014_009 (right). Each point represents one subject; horizontal lines show the dataset mean. Grey points indicate baseline (full-repetition) values; coloured points indicate values at θ^* . Subjects are ordered by validation AUC.

Table 1: **Supplementary Table S1.** Per-subject results at the Pareto-optimal threshold θ^* for BigP3BCI ($\theta^* = 3.5$ nats, $\theta_{\text{norm}} = 0.818$, $N = 72$, $r_{\text{max}} = 5$) and BNCI2014_009 ($\theta^* = 2.5$ nats, $\theta_{\text{norm}} = 0.697$, $N = 36$, $r_{\text{max}} = 8$). Subjects are ordered by validation AUC (ascending) within each dataset. BNCI AUC is a per-subject letter accuracy proxy (no separate validation epoch set; see Section 2.2). † Individual accuracy drop exceeds the ≤ 5 pp threshold; the Pareto constraint is applied at the *dataset-mean* level. $\text{b/m} = \text{bits per minute}$.

Subject	AUC	Accuracy				ITR (b/m)			
		Baseline (%)	At θ^* (%)	Δ (pp)	Δ	Baseline	At θ^*	Δ	Reps saved
<i>BigP3BCI</i> — 12 subjects, 398 letters total									
A09	0.70	14.3	14.3	0.0	0.0	2.1	2.1	0.0	0.0
A05	0.72	55.6	51.9	-3.7	-3.7	16.5	15.4	-1.0	0.2
A15	0.75	57.1	54.3	-2.9	-2.9	17.2	16.2	-1.0	0.1
A14	0.78	74.3	62.9	-11.4†	-11.4†	25.4	22.5	-2.9	0.6
A16	0.79	45.7	42.9	-2.9	-2.9	12.4	11.4	-0.9	0.1
A03	0.80	78.6	82.1	+3.6	+3.6	27.7	33.5	+5.9	0.6
A19	0.80	74.3	74.3	0.0	0.0	25.4	26.9	+1.5	0.3
A07	0.81	96.4	92.9	-3.6	-3.6	38.6	47.5	+8.8	1.2
A01	0.83	91.4	85.7	-5.7	-5.7	35.2	37.2	+2.0	0.8
A02	0.84	80.0	74.3	-5.7	-5.7	28.4	31.4	+2.9	1.0
A04	0.88	94.3	88.6	-5.7	-5.7	37.1	49.3	+12.2	1.7
A06	0.88	97.1	94.3	-2.9	-2.9	39.1	51.8	+12.6	1.5
<i>Mean</i>	0.80	71.6	68.2	-3.4	-3.4	25.4	28.8	+3.3	0.67
<i>BNCI2014_009</i> — 10 subjects, 180 letters total									
S03	0.72	72.2	55.6	-16.7†	-16.7†	17.0	18.8	+1.8	3.4
S08	0.89	88.9	72.2	-16.7†	-16.7†	24.1	24.1	+0.0	2.5
S01	0.94	94.4	94.4	0.0	0.0	26.9	31.4	+4.5	1.2
S02	0.94	94.4	100.0	+5.6	+5.6	26.9	50.6	+23.7	3.4
S04	0.94	94.4	94.4	0.0	0.0	26.9	39.6	+12.7	2.7
S05	0.94	94.4	94.4	0.0	0.0	26.9	44.3	+17.4	3.3
S06	1.00	100.0	88.9	-11.1†	-11.1†	30.4	31.0	+0.6	1.9
S07	1.00	100.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	30.4	34.5	+4.1	1.0
S09	1.00	100.0	94.4	-5.6	-5.6	30.4	47.9	+17.5	3.7
S10	1.00	100.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	30.4	53.5	+23.1	3.7
<i>Mean</i>	0.94	93.9	89.4	-4.4	-4.4	27.0	37.6	+10.5	2.69